

Site Identification Analysis for Airborne Wind Energy devices

Case Study: Ireland

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	Name	Date
Prepared	Inés Coca, Emma Geoghegan	12/11/2024
Reviewed	Oisín Duffy, Louise O'Boyle	05/12/2024
	Kristian Petrick (Airborne Wind Europe)	17/12/2024
Approved	Louise O'Boyle Marlène Moutel (Laminak Energy)	26/12/2024

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Executive Summary

This report outlines the methodology and findings of a site identification analysis for Airborne Wind Energy (AWE) systems in Ireland, conducted as part of the DEM-AWE project. Using Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and publicly available datasets, the analysis evaluates the suitability of sites for AWE device deployment, considering environmental, geographic, and logistical factors. It builds on methodologies developed for a previous study in Germany Coca-Tagarro, I. (2023), adapting them to Ireland's unique context.

Site identification criteria were defined to account for slope, operational radius, proximity to settlements, and other constraints, ensuring adaptability to various AWE technologies.

High-quality geospatial data from sources including OpenStreetMap, NASA, and Copernicus were analysed using QGIS to identify suitable locations. Variations in operational radius, buffer zones, and distance to forests were assessed to understand their impact on site availability.

Model outputs were cross-referenced with manual analyses and developer feedback, achieving a 100% match with verified sites. The base case identified between 1,600–1,800 km² of deployment area and 9,300–10,700 km² of operational area which translates to almost 6,000 sites and up to 24,000 devices supporting up to over 30 GW of AWE capacity. Sensitivity analysis revealed that the operational radius significantly impacts site availability, with shorter tethers enabling higher deployment densities. County Mayo, County Donegal, and County Kerry emerged as high-potential areas due to their geography and low population density.

Ireland offers a promising landscape for AWE, owing in part to greater land availability compared to countries like Germany, attributed to lower population density and less forest coverage.

Operational radius plays a critical role in deployment potential, highlighting the need for tailored strategies for different technologies. Data gaps, particularly in building classification and forest cover, present challenges, emphasising the need for refined datasets and ground validation prior to final site selection. This study underscores Ireland's strategic potential for AWE development, contributing to renewable energy targets and fostering innovation in high-altitude wind technologies.

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List of Abbreviations

AWE	Airborne Wind Energy
CRS	Coordinate reference System
DEM	Digital Elevation Model
ETRS89	European Terrestrial Reference System 1989
EPSG:3035	European Projection System Grid
GS	Ground Station
IAA	Irish Aviation Authority
kW	KiloWatt
MW	MegaWatt
ODbL	Open Database License
OSM	Open Street Map
SRTM	Shuttle Radar Topography Mission
TIFF	Tagged Image File Format
QGIS	Open-source GIS software used for geospatial analysis

1 Introduction

This report details the methodology followed to identify suitable sites for the development of Airborne Wind Energy (AWE) farms in Ireland using publicly available datasets and GIS tools.

The analysis follows the general methodology detailed in *“Site Identification Analysis for AWE Devices. A case study in Germany”* Coca-Tagarro, I. (2023). Some variations to the existing methodology were applied after learnings extracted from the German analysis and the engagement with new developers. These improvements comprised the additions of new sensitivity cases, including variations in the operational radius to capture the effects of shorter tether lengths. Additionally, the wind resource was not considered as a parameter given the results obtained in Germany and observation that this is an overly simplistic and restrictive parameter.

This report is one of a suite of reports providing individual analysis results for Ireland, the Netherlands, France and Spain. While the core approach remained consistent across all analysed countries, specific adaptations were made to account for each country's unique characteristics in data and geographic context. The data processing workflow was uniform across the analysed countries. The following sections outline the data sources, feature selection, analysis methodology, quality control procedures, and results of the Ireland-specific analysis.

2 Identification Criteria

The criteria for this project were refined and expanded from those used in previous work undertaken as part of the MegaAWE project Coca-Tagarro, I. (2023), originally established through extensive consultations with various industry developers. These engagements led to the development of several site identification criteria, specific requirements for AWE devices, and the definition of key parameter variations to conduct sensitivity analyses while maintaining a technology-agnostic approach. This approach seeks to meet the needs and preferences of individual technologies without showing favouritism toward any particular one. It establishes an impartial evaluation framework, offering valuable insights relevant across the industry, encouraging innovation, and supporting well-informed decision-making.

As part of the DEM-AWE project, additional consultations were conducted with further technology developers, resulting in the adjustment of certain criteria and parameters, as well as the addition of sensitivity variations to reflect insights from these discussions and lessons learned from the outcomes observed in Germany. Across both MegaAWE and DEM-AWE projects engagement included consultation with the following technology developers: Enerkite, Kitekraft, Kitepower, Skysails, TwingTec, WindFisher and Ampyx Power (now dissolved but core activity continued by Fuchszeug/Mozaero).

Table 2.1. Criteria, requirements and sensitivity analysis applied to the site identification analysis.

CRITERIA	REQUIREMENT AWE DEVICES	SENSITIVITY STUDIES
Flat in operating and surrounding area	Avoid areas with >30° slope in the deployment areas.	
Co-use, e.g. agricultural land use	Yes	
Operational Radius around ground station	Base Case: 425m	Op. radius: 300, 650,850 and 1050m.
Inhabited urban area/ Settlements in general/ Publicly used infrastructure (e.g., roads, railways)	Avoid. Apply Operational Area radius. Additionally, add Risk buffer. Risk buffer Base Case: 100m distance from Ground Station	Risk buffers: 0, 50, 150m.
High structures (e.g., wind turbines, power lines, phone, met and radio masts)	Avoid. Apply Operational Area radius. 100m Safety buffer around high structures.	
Air Traffic	Avoid. 5000m Risk buffer around Airports. 1760m Risk buffer around Airfields	
Forests	Avoid. Permitted to fly partially over forests. Base Case: 200m distance from Ground Station	Distance from GS: 100 and 300m.
Water bodies	Avoid. Permitted to fly partially over Water Bodies. Base Case Min Distance from Ground Station: 100m.	
Protected Areas		
Military Areas	Avoid. Apply Operational Area radius	

Figure 2.1. Diagram on the criteria and requirements applied for the site identification analysis. GS refers to "Ground Station".

3 Data sources and features selection

Identifying suitable locations for AWE systems requires collecting data on environmental, geographical, logistical, and site-specific factors relevant to the technology's requirements.

Several datasets were selected from publicly available sources such as OpenStreetMap Contributors (ODbL), NASA JPL (2013)¹, Ireland's Open Data Portal²European Union's Copernicus Land Monitoring Service information³ , Tailte Éireann Surveying Open Data Portal⁴, Irish lights and Irish Aviation Agency (IAA). Most of the datasets used were accessed as shapefiles, raster/TIFF (Tagged Image File Format) files or Aeronautical charts. However, collecting detailed, accurate and current data can be difficult for certain variables, and some data sources present gaps in information (e.g., complete dataset on settlements). An effort was made to obtain at least two different datasets for each criterion to ensure validation and accuracy.

Table 3.1. Main parameters, source and dataset format.

Parameter	Source	Format
Base map	OSM, 2024	Shapefiles
Slope	NASA JPL, 2013	TIFF
Protected Areas	Ireland's Open Data Portal, 2024	Shapefiles
Water bodies	Tailte Éireann, 2024; OSM, 2024	Shapefiles
Forests	Copernicus, 2024	TIFF
Settlements	Tailte Éireann, 2024; OSM, 2024	Shapefiles
Military Areas	OSM, 2024	Shapefiles
High structures	Irish Lights, 2024; OSM, 2024	Shapefiles
Roads	OSM, 2024	Shapefiles
Railways	OSM, 2024	Shapefiles
Air Traffic	Tailte Éireann, 2024; OSM, 2024	Shapefiles, Aeronautical charts

¹ NASA JPL (2013). NASA Shuttle Radar Topography Mission Global 1 arc second [Data set]. NASA EOSDIS Land Processes Distributed Active Archive Center (LP DAAC). Accessed 2024-03-13 from <https://doi.org/10.5067/MEaSURES/SRTM/SRTMGL1.003>

² Data.gov.ie licensed under CC BY 4.0

³ <https://doi.org/10.2909/59b0620c-7bb4-4c82-b3ce-f16715573137> licensed under CC BY 4.0

⁴ licensed under CC BY 4.0

The data analysis came from the following datasets from which a wide range of data was collected, extracted, and used:

- **NASA Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM):** The SRTM dataset, managed by NASA's Land Processes Distributed Active Archive Center, offers a near-global digital elevation model (DEM) derived from radar interferometry. This dataset, created from data collected during the Space Shuttle Endeavour's STS-99 mission (February 11, 2000), provides elevation information for about 80% of Earth's landmass with a spatial resolution of 1 arc-second (~30 meters). SRTM data fills any voids by merging topographic sources as needed, with version 3 being a void-free global dataset. This data was accessed in March 2024 and was used in the analysis to derive **slope information**.
- **Ireland's Open Data Portal, 2024:** Data on **protected areas** in Ireland, including "Special Areas of Conservation", "Special Protection Areas", "Natural Heritage Areas", "Dublin Bay Biosphere", and "National Monuments Service - World Heritage Properties," was accessed from Ireland's Open Data Portal (data.gov.ie) in 2024. Ireland's Open Data Portal serves as a national repository for public data, aiming to enhance transparency, support innovation, and facilitate research by making a wide range of governmental data available under the Creative Commons Attribution (CC-BY) licence.
- **OpenStreetMap (OSM):** OpenStreetMap is a freely accessible, user-contributed geographic database. Volunteers worldwide contribute and maintain its data, ensuring high completeness and accuracy, particularly in European regions. This dataset was used for a **wide range of criteria** specified in **Error! Reference source not found..** such as railways, military areas, settlements, etc.
- **Forest Type, EU Copernicus (2018):** This raster dataset offers a forest classification layer with 10-meter spatial resolution, distinguishing three classes: non-forest areas, broadleaved

forests, and coniferous forests. Created under the EU Copernicus program by the European Environment Agency in 2020, this High-Resolution Layer Forest Type product aligns with the FAO forest definition.

- **Tailte Éireann Surveying Open Data Portal (2024):** This Data Portal Provides official mapping, surveying, and geographic data for Ireland. Tailte Éireann serves as Ireland's national mapping and land registration authority, offering public access to accurate geographic datasets and ensuring compliance with national and EU standards for open data usage. Airfield Areas, Generalised Settlements, and National 250k Map with watercourses were sourced here.
- **Irish Lights:** Data on the geographic positions of **lighthouses** was obtained from the Commissioners of Irish Lights, commonly referred to as Irish Lights. Irish Lights functions as the general lighthouse authority for both Northern Ireland and the Republic of Ireland, overseeing the safety of navigational aids along coasts and maritime regions to promote safe travel through adjacent seas and islands.
- **Irish Aviation Agency (IAA) Visual Flight Rules (VFR) Airspace Chart:** This VFR airspace chart, scale 1:500,000, provided by the Irish Aviation Authority, is intended for visual flight navigation within the Shannon FIR boundaries. Version 4 of this chart is freely available for download and was used in mapping airspace restrictions for aviation-related considerations. This chart should be referenced with the statement: "Contains data from the Irish Aviation Authority's VFR Airspace Chart, Scale 1:500,000, freely available for public use."

After accessing the datasets, only some of the layers and specific portions of the raw layers were used⁵. To ensure a robust analysis, a thorough process was conducted to determine which layers, and the specific features from each layer, would be included in the input data. The first step involved comparing and cross-checking the information in layers that contained data on the same criteria. Consequently, the features of each layer that aligned with the predetermined selection criteria and parameters were identified. Following this, a thorough visual inspection was conducted on the raw layers and their features, with a minimum of 20 randomly selected features reviewed in three different counties using GIS and satellite imagery. This inspection aimed to confirm whether the layers and the selected features should be retained or excluded from further analysis. Based on the visual inspection and the defined selection criteria, key features were extracted from each layer and processed (see Section 4) to meet AWE requirements (e.g., identifying relevant high structures and applying safety buffers around them).

⁵ To enhance validation and accuracy, we aimed to acquire at least two datasets for each criterion. However, it was not always necessary to include all the sourced layers in the final analysis. Only the most accurate and complete datasets were retained, or specific parts that complemented other datasets were used.

Table 3.2. Table presenting the selected features from each used dataset.

CRITERIA	Open Street Map (2024)	Others
Base map	Counties basemaps	
Slope	N/A	NASA JPL (2013). NASA Shuttle Radar Topography Mission Global 1 arc second NetCDF
Protected Areas	N/A	Special Protection Area (Birds Directive) Special Areas of Conservation (Habitats Directive) Natural Heritage Areas Dublin Bay Biosphere UNESCO World Heritage Properties
Water Bodies	<p>Water</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water • Riverbank • Reservoir • Dock • Wetland 	<p>Waterways</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Canal • River • Stream
Forests		Copernicus – Forest cover
Settlements	<p>Land Use</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Allotments • Cemetery • Commercial • Farmyard 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Industrial • Recreational Ground • Residential • Retail • Park <p>Tailte Éireann (2024) Settlements Generalised 20100m – National Statistical Boundaries – 2015</p>
Military Area	<p>Land Use</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Military 	

CRITERIA	Open Street Map (2024)	Others
High structures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Wind Turbines Lighthouse Power Cable Points <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Comms tower • Observation tower • Tower • Water tower • Windmill 	Irish Lights (2024) – Lighthouse locations
Roads	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Roads <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Motorway • Motorway link • Primary • Primary link • Residential • Secondary 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Secondary link • Tertiary • Tertiary link • Trunk • Trunk link • Unclassified <p>N/A</p>
Railways	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Railways <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rail • Tram 	
Air Traffic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Transport <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Helipad • Airfield • Apron • Airport 	Irish Aviation Authority (IAA)(2017) VFR Airspace Chart Scale 1:500,000

4 Data extraction and Site identification methodology using QGIS Models

4.1 Data Collection and Extraction

The data collection for all the different criteria specified in Table 3.1 was carried out utilising various datasets with different characteristics. OSM, Tailte Éireann, NPWS, IAA and Copernicus datasets had a coverage for the entirety of Ireland. However, the data processing was carried out at Irish provinces level. A QGIS project was created for each one of the Irish provinces (excluding the portion of Ulster specific to Northern Ireland). All the data extraction analysis were made using a 5km-buffered base map⁶ of the relevant region. The subsections below list every layer, category, and feature utilised for each criterion.

The data extraction of the relevant categories and features of each raw layer was automated using the Graphical Modeller and batch process tool in QGIS. All the inputs from the batch process were stored as .json files to be able to carry out a quality control on this step. The outputs from the Data Extraction process were 11 layers by province containing the relevant data for each criterion. All the layers received a systematic name, containing the criteria, the CRS and the region code 'XXX' (E.g, Leinster=LEN):

- Slope_3035_XXX
- Protected_Areas_3035_XXX
- Water_Bodies_3035_XXX
- Forests_3035_XXX

⁶ A 5 km buffer was added to the base maps of the different regions to account the presence of objects that, even though located outside the state division, could still affect areas within the state or study region due to their predefined range (For example, airports located in an adjacent state, outside the studied region, but which exclusion boundary (5 km) could affect areas within the studied region).

- Settlements_3035_XXX
- Settlements2_3035_XXX
- Military_Areas_3035_XXX
- High_Structures_3035_XXX
- Roads_3035_XXX
- Railways_3035_XXX
- Air_Traffic_3035_XXX

EPSG:3035 (ETRS89, LAEA) was selected as the Coordinate reference system and all raw layers used were reprojected to meet this Coordinate Reference System (CRS). The data extraction steps adopted are detailed in the subsections below.

4.1.1 Base Map

All base maps used were extracted from Townlands.ie, a repository offering geographic data on Ireland's townlands, electoral divisions, civil parishes, baronies, and counties. The data is derived from OpenStreetMap and comply with the Open Database License (ODbL).

Figure 4.1. Base map. Example: Connacht.

Source Data: ©OpenStreetMap Contributors (ODbL)

4.1.2 Slope

The criteria requirement was to avoid areas with a slope of more than 30 degrees (following the methodology established for this criterion in Germany⁷).

The data used for the slope was extracted in March 2024 from the AppEEARS (<https://lpdaac.usgs.gov/products/srtmgl1v003/>) portal. The layer used “SRTMGL1_DEM (SRTMGL1_NC.003)” was a DEM (Digital Elevation Model) generated by NASA Shuttle Radar Topography Mission, with a pixel size of ~30m.

The *Slope* tool was used to calculate the slope in the raster layer. The raster was reclassified using the *raster calculator*, applying the value of 1 to areas with a slope less than 30 degrees and applying

⁷ Coca-Tagarro, I. (2023). Site Identification Analysis for AWE Devices. A case study in Germany (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10462306>

a value of 0 to areas with more than 30 degrees. To transform the raster into a vector layer the *polygonize* tool was used and features with a value equal to 0 were erased. The final vector was *clipped* to the Irish basemap.

Figure 4.2. Areas in purple meet the slope requirement (<30°). Example: Connacht.

Source Data: ©OpenStreetMap Contributors (ODbL), NASA JPL

Note: No buffer was applied around the excluded slope in order to avoid excluding areas where the GS deployment area is at a higher elevation than the terrain surrounding it. It is expected that the AWE farms at a commercial level can control the deployment and landing of the aircrafts and avoid the terrain with steep slope. Further investigation on a case-by-case basis would be required to identify if GS cannot be deployed in an area that has been identified as “deployment area”.

4.1.3 Protected Areas

The requirement for this criterion was to avoid protected areas and flying over these areas was not permitted. A 425m operational radius buffer was applied as the base case. Sensitivity analysis on the operational radius includes 300, 650, 850 and 1050m scenarios.

Data containing information on Protected Areas were sourced from Ireland's Open Data Portal (2024) (<https://data.gov.ie/>). The layers used were “Special Areas of Conservation”, “Special Protection Areas”, “Natural Heritage Areas” and “Dublin Bay Biosphere”. The layers were downloaded in January 2024. The layer “National Monuments Service - World Heritage Properties” containing UNESCO world heritage sites, was accessed and downloaded in April 2024.

The location of the UNESCO sites in Ireland were included in separate layers that were *merged* in QGIS to create one unified UNESCO layer. The tool *fix geometries* was used on “Special Areas of Conservation”, “Special Protection Areas” and “Natural Heritage Areas” layers, using the structure repair method. All 5 layers were *clipped* to the 5km-buffered basemap, and the tool *retain fields* was used on all the layers to preserve only the identifying fields. The layers were then *merged*.

The operational radius was applied in a later stage, specified in section **Error! Reference source not found.** - **Error! Reference source not found.**

Figure 4.3. Protected Areas (shown in red) Example: Connacht.

Source Data: ©OpenStreetMap Contributors (ODbL), ©Ireland's Open Data Portal (CC BY 4.0)

4.1.4 Water Bodies

The requirement for this layer was to avoid water bodies as deployment areas and leave a 100m distance to the GS. Flying over these areas is permitted.

The Databases used to obtain data on water bodies in Ireland were:

- National 250k Map of Ireland (2022) - Containing data on watercourses with a drainage basin >500m², the dataset was accessed and download in February 2024 from Tailte Éireanns Surveying Open Data Portal website ([Water - National 250k Map Of Ireland - Dataset - data.gov.ie](https://data.gov.ie)).
- OSM (2024) – two layers were used:
 - “Water” that contains data on water bodies. The categories included in the analyses were ‘Dock’, ‘Reservoir’, ‘Riverbank’, and ‘Water’.
 - “Waterways” is a lines layer that contains data on watercourses, where the only the categories ‘canal’ and ‘river’ were selected.

Both layers were accessed and downloaded in February 2024 from (<https://download.geofabrik.de/>)

All layers were clipped to a 5km-buffered basemap. A visual inspection and comparison of the National 250k layer and the OSM datasets showed that, while the OSM waterways layer was more complete, it contained some misclassifications of rivers as 'streams'. To correct these, the National 250k layer was used to identify streams that should be classified as rivers within the OSM waterways dataset.

To facilitate this, a 10m *buffer* was applied to the National 250k layer, and the misclassified streams in the OSM waterways layer were extracted using the *extract by location* tool. The extracted layer was then *merged* with the OSM waterways layer, retaining only the 'canal' and 'river' categories (using the *extract by expression* tool). A 5m *buffer* was added to this merged layer to account for waterway width, ensuring accuracy in mapping canals, rivers, and corrected "streams."

To include additional relevant water bodies, the *extract by expression* tool was used to select appropriate categories from the OSM water layer. Finally, the layers from these last two steps were *merged*, and the *retain fields* tool was used to keep only fields with unique identifiers for each feature and their category names.

The 100m distance from water bodies to the ground station required was applied in a later stage, specified in section **Error! Reference source not found. - Error! Reference source not found.**

Figure 4.4. Water Bodies (shown in blue). Example: Connacht.

Source Data: ©OpenStreetMap Contributors (ODbL), © Tailte Éireann (CC BY 4.0)

4.1.5 Forests

The requirement for this criterion was to avoid forests as deployment areas and leave a 200m distance between the GS and forest cover. Flying over these areas is permitted and sensitivity analysis on the distance to forests includes 100 and 300m scenarios.

The dataset used to obtain data on forests was the Copernicus Forest Type 2018 (raster 10 m Europe, 3-yearly cover), which was accessed and downloaded through Copernicus' land monitoring service website ([Dataset catalogue — Copernicus Land Monitoring Service](#)) in April 2024. The data was downloaded in raster format, and several layers were downloaded to cover Irish land. The values 1 (Broadleaf Forest) and 2 (Coniferous Forest) were used.

The *raster calculator* tool was used to extract the areas with the forest cover of interest. All pixels with values less than 1 and greater than 2 were multiplied by 0 and values equal to 1 and 2 were multiplied by 1. The resulting layer was a raster only containing the features 0 and 1. The tool

translate (convert format) was then used and the 0 feature was assigned a no-data value. The tool *polygonise* was used on the resulting layer to convert the layer from raster to vector. This process was then applied to all the layers and the final vectorized layers were merged under one forest cover layer.

This forest layer was then *clipped* to the 5km-buffered basemap and *retain fields* was used to extract only the fields with identifying values.

The distance to forest radius was applied in a later stage, specified in section **Error! Reference source not found.** - **Error! Reference source not found..**

Figure 4.5. Forests (shown in green). Example: Connacht.

Source Data: ©OpenStreetMap Contributors (ODbL), © Copernicus (CC BY 4.0)

4.1.6 Settlements

The requirement applied to this criterion was to avoid settlements and flying over these areas was not permitted. A 425m operational radius buffer was applied as the base case. Sensitivity analysis on the operational radius includes 300, 650, 850 and 1050m scenarios. Additionally, a risk buffer of 100m is applied in the base case for this criterion (as part of publicly used infrastructure). Sensitivity analysis on the risk buffer includes 0, 50 and 150m buffers.

The databases used to obtain data on Settlements in Ireland were:

- Settlements Generalised 20m – National Statistical Boundaries – 2015 (2022), accessed and downloaded from Tailte Éireann’s Surveying Open Data Portal website (<https://data-osi.opendata.arcgis.com/>) in June 2024. – This dataset outlines boundaries for urban and rural settlements, distinguishing Census towns and cities based on population clusters (minimum of 50 occupied dwellings with a 100-meter maximum spacing) and proximity criteria (extensions include dwellings within 100 meters of an existing boundary). It includes generalized boundaries at a 20-meter resolution, reflecting updates through 2015.
- OSM (2024) – Two layers were used from this dataset:
 - The OSM layer on Land use which “fclass” categories ‘Allotments’, ‘Cemetery’, ‘Commercial’, ‘Farmyard’, ‘Industrial’, ‘Park’, ‘Recreation_ground’, ‘Residential’, and ‘Retail’ were used.
 - The OSM layer on Buildings. The “type” categories used include: 'allotment_house', 'apartments', 'bakehouse', 'bank', 'bungalow', 'caravan', 'carport', 'castle', 'cathedral', 'chapel', 'church', 'civic', 'clinic', 'clubhouse', 'college', 'commercial', 'commercial;house', 'community_hall', 'convent', 'detached', 'dormitory', 'fire_station', 'hall', 'historic', 'hospital', 'hostel', 'hotel', 'house', 'house;commercial', 'house;retail', 'industrial', 'kindergarten', 'kiosk', 'manor', 'manufacture', 'mausoleum', 'mess_hall', 'military', 'mobile_home', 'monastery', 'nursing_home', 'office', 'outbuilding', 'parking', 'passageway', 'post_office', 'presbytery', 'pub', 'public', 'reception', 'religious',

'residential', 'restaurant', 'retail', 'school', 'security_booth', 'semi', 'semidetached_house', 'service', 'shelter', 'sports_centre', 'sports_hall', 'stadium', 'static_caravan', 'station', 'terminal', 'terrace', 'theatre', 'toilets', 'train_station', 'transportation', 'tribune', 'university' and 'utility'.

OSM data was accessed and downloaded from Geofabrik's free download server (<https://download.geofabrik.de/>) in February 2024.

After inspecting the OSM buildings layer, it became clear that some buildings were not classified in the 'type' category, preventing a comprehensive inclusion of all relevant buildings in the analysis. To assess the impact of these misclassifications on the final analysis results, the analysis was conducted twice. Firstly, without the OSM buildings layer entirely, and then a second time, including only correctly classified features of that layer. In this second run, the proportion of unclassified features and the buildings of interest was calculated.

After completing both analyses, a correction factor was determined based on the impact of the correctly classified buildings of interest on the overall results. This factor was then adjusted to account for the estimated impact of the misclassified buildings that might have been relevant gaps as described in Section 4.2.2.1.

Additionally, it's important to note that the completeness of the OSM buildings layer varied by county in Ireland. As shown in the image below (Figure 4.6), some counties have more detailed information than others, which affects the calculation of deployment areas that appear on the final maps.

Figure 4.6. Map showing the OSM buildings layer (on the left) in Ireland. The image on the right (in red) shows the only the features of interest that were part of the analysis.

The three layers were *clipped* to the 5km buffered basemap. To extract the settlements without including the buildings layer, the tool *extract by expression* was used on the OSM landuse layer maintaining the relevant categories and the output was *merged* to the “Settlements Generalised 20m” layer. *Retain fields* was used to retain only the identifying fields, obtaining the “Settlements_3035_XXX” layer.

When including the OSM buildings layer, the *difference* tool was used with the raw layer and the “Settlements_3035_XXX” output to avoid including buildings that were already accounted for in the other layers. The *extract by expression* tool was used to retain only the relevant categories and the resulting layer was *merged* to the “Buildings_3035_XXX” layer. *Retain fields* was used once again, obtaining “Settlements2_3035_XXX”.

The operational radius and risk buffer were applied in a later stage, specified in section **Error! Reference source not found.** - **Error! Reference source not found.**

Figure 4.7. Settlements (shown in brown) including the ‘Buildings’ layer. Example: Connacht.

Source Data: ©OpenStreetMap Contributors (ODbL), © Tailte Éireann (CC BY 4.0)

4.1.7 Military Areas

The requirement for this criterion was to avoid military areas and flying over these areas was not permitted. A 425m operational radius buffer was applied as the base case. Sensitivity analysis on the operational radius includes 300, 650, 850 and 1050m.

The database used to obtain the relevant information was from OSM (2024) downloaded and accessed in February 2024 from (<https://download.geofabrik.de/>) - The layer on Land Use containing the category ‘Military’ was used.

The layer was *clipped* to the 5km-buffered basemap and the relevant category was extracted using the *extract by expression* tool in QGIS. The tool *retain fields* was applied to preserve only the features containing a unique identifier.

The operational radius was applied in a later stage, specified in section **Error! Reference source not found.** - **Error! Reference source not found.**

Figure 4.8. Military areas (shown in pink). Example: Connacht.

Source Data: ©OpenStreetMap Contributors (ODbL)

4.1.8 High Structures

The requirement for High Structures was to avoid them and leave a 100m safety buffer around them. Flying over these structures was not permitted. A 425m operational radius buffer was applied as the base case. Sensitivity analysis on the operational radius includes 300, 650, 850 and 1050m.

Various categories were included under high structures for this analysis including: wind turbines, power cables, lighthouses and other towers (such as communication, observation and water towers). These layers were processed individually and then combined into a final 'high structures' layer.

The following sections go into further detail of processes applied to each of the layers included in the final high structures layer.

4.1.8.1 Wind Turbines

The database used to obtain data regarding wind turbine locations was OSM (2024). A points vector layer containing the locations of wind turbines in Ireland was used. OSM data was accessed and downloaded from the QuickOSM plugin in QGIS in February 2024. The key used for this search was “Man Made/Power/Power Generator/Wind Turbine” and was downloaded on a province level.

The layers were *clipped* to the 5km-buffered basemap, and the tool *retain fields* was used to preserve only the unique identifying features. A 50m *buffer* was also applied to account for the dimensions of the turbines.

4.1.8.2 Power lines / Power stations

The database used to collect data on power lines and power stations was OSM (2024). A line vector layer containing the locations of power cables in Ireland was used. OSM data was accessed and downloaded from the QuickOSM plugin in QGIS in February 2024. The key used for the search was “Man made/Power/Power Cable” and was downloaded on a province level. The layers were *clipped* to the 5km-buffered basemap and the tool *retain fields* was used to preserve only the unique identifying features. A 5m *buffer* was also applied to account for the width of the power lines.

4.1.8.3 Lighthouses

The databases used to obtain data on towers were:

- OSM (2024) – The layer used was a points shapefile layer containing the locations of lighthouses in Ireland downloaded and accessed from the QuickOSM plugin in QGIS in

February 2024. The key used for the search was “Man made/Man made/Lighthouse”.

The lighthouses were downloaded on a national level.

- Irish lights – After contacting with info@irishlights.ie a vector layer on location of lighthouses in Ireland was shared with us.

Following a visual examination of the two lighthouse layers using satellite images, it became clear that both layers were complimentary, making it necessary to merge and combine the points that were unique to each dataset. Both layers were loaded into a QGIS project and merged, and a manual cleaning of duplicated points and refining of the location was done using the toggle editing tool and satellite images. The final layer was then saved under one singular lighthouse layer.

This layer was *clipped* to the 5km-buffered basemap and the tool *retain fields* was used to preserve only the unique identifying features. A 10m *buffer* was also applied to account for the width of the lighthouses.

4.1.8.4 Other towers

The database used to obtain data regarding towers locations was OSM (2024). The vector layer called Points containing the categories ‘comms_tower’, ‘observation_tower’, ‘tower’, ‘water_tower’ and ‘windmill’, which was downloaded and accessed from (<https://download.geofabrik.de/>) in February 2024 was used.

The layer was *clipped* to the 5km-buffered basemap. The tool *extract by expression* was used to filter the categories of interest and with the output, the tool *retain fields* was used to preserve only the unique identifying features. A 10m *buffer* was also applied to account for the width of the towers.

The output layers of Wind turbines, power cables, lighthouses and other towers were merged and a safety buffer of 100m was added.

The operational radius was applied in a later stage, specified in section **Error! Reference source not found.** - **Error! Reference source not found.**

Figure 4.9. High structures (shown in black). Example: Connacht.

Source Data: ©OpenStreetMap Contributors (ODbL), ©Irish lights

4.1.9 Roads

The requirement applied to this criterion was to avoid roads and flying over these structures was not permitted. A 425m operational radius buffer was applied as the base case. Sensitivity analysis on the operational radius includes 300, 650, 850 and 1050m scenarios. Additionally, a risk buffer of 100m is applied in the base case for this criterion (as part of publicly used infrastructure). Sensitivity analysis on the risk buffer includes 0, 50 and 150m buffers.

The data regarding roads was sourced from Open Street Map accessed in February 2024 from (<https://download.geofabrik.de/>) – The layer on roads containing the categories ‘motorway’,

'motorway_link', 'primary', 'Primary_link', 'residential', 'secondary', 'secondary_link', 'tertiary', 'tertiary_link', 'trunk', 'trunk link' and 'unclassified' was used.

The layer was *clipped* to the 5km-buffered basemap. The tool *extract by expression* was used to extract the categories of interest from the layer. A *buffer* of 5m was applied to account for the width of the roads and the tool *retain fields* was used to preserve only the features containing identifiers.

The operational radius and risk buffer were applied in a later stage, specified in section **Error! Reference source not found.** - **Error! Reference source not found.**

Figure 4.10. Roads (shown in green). Example: Connacht.

Source Data: ©OpenStreetMap Contributors (ODbL)

4.1.10 Railways

The requirement applied to this criterion was to avoid railways and flying over these structures was not permitted. A 425m operational radius buffer was applied as the base case. Sensitivity analysis

on the operational radius includes 300, 650, 850 and 1050m scenarios. Additionally, a risk buffer of 100m is applied in the base case for this criterion (as part of publicly used infrastructure). Sensitivity analysis on the risk buffer includes 0, 50 and 150m buffers.

The data used for railways was sourced from OSM (2024) downloaded and accessed in February 2024 from (<https://download.geofabrik.de/>). The categories 'rail' and 'tram' were used.

The layer was *clipped* to the 5km buffered basemap. The tool *extract by expression* was used to extract the selected categories from the layer. A 5m *buffer* was then applied to account for the railways width and the tool *retain fields* was used to preserve only the features containing identifiers.

The operational radius and risk buffer were applied in a later stage, specified in section **Error! Reference source not found.** - **Error! Reference source not found.**

Figure 4.11. Railways (shown in red). Example: Connacht.

Source Data: ©OpenStreetMap Contributors (ODbL)

4.1.11 Air Traffic

The requirement for this criterion was to avoid airspace restricted areas and flying over these areas was not permitted. A 425m operational radius buffer was applied as the base case. Sensitivity analysis on the operational radius includes 300, 650, 850 and 1050m scenarios. Additionally, a 5000m buffer was applied around airports and 1760m buffer was applied around airfields following the methodology implemented in Germany.

4.1.11.1 Airspace Restricted Areas

The data used for restricted airspace came from the Irish Aviation Agency, under aeronautical charts (<https://www.iaa.ie/commercial-aviation/airspace/aeronautical-charts>) accessed and georeferenced in 2021. Only the categories ‘prohibited area’ and ‘danger & restricted areas’ were used.

The layer was *clipped* to the 5km buffered basemap. The tool *extract by expression* was used to extract the selected categories of interest from the layer.

4.1.11.2 Airports

The dataset used for airports was sourced from Tailte Éireanns Surveying Open Data Portal – Using the layer “Airfield Area - National 250K Map of Ireland” (<https://data.gov.ie>), downloaded and accessed in February 2024. This layer contained Military, commercial and leisure airports and airfields with area ≥ 0.4 km² and some of them would fall under the airfields classification. Therefore, only the OBJECTID 2, 3, 5, 6, 8 and 9 were selected.

The layer was *clipped* to the 5km-buffered basemap. The tool *extract by expression* was used to extract the selected categories from the layer and a 5000m *buffer* was added to the layer.

4.1.11.3 Airfields

The data used for airfield areas was obtained from OSM (2024), downloaded and accessed in February 2024 from (<https://download.geofabrik.de/>). The Transport layer containing the categories 'airfield', 'airport', 'apron' and 'helipad' was used.

The layer was *clipped* to the 5km-buffered basemap. The tool *extract by expression* was used to extract the selected categories from the layer and a 1760m *buffer* was added to the layer.

All three layers were then *merged* and the tool *retain fields* was used to preserve only the features containing identifiers.

The operational radius was applied in a later stage, specified in section **Error! Reference source not found.** - **Error! Reference source not found.**

Figure 4.12. Air Traffic (shown in orange). Example: Connacht.

Source Data: ©OpenStreetMap Contributors (ODbL), © Tailte Éireann (CC BY 4.0), ©IAA

4.2 Data Processing

4.2.1 Site Identification

For the site identification process, new QGIS projects were created for the four provinces, and the analysis was applied individually to each region. The results were eventually integrated to generate final maps including information for the whole Republic of Ireland.

A model was constructed in the Graphical Modeller to incorporate various parameters and conduct sensitivity analysis on the criteria. All the input layers consisted of the layers obtained through the Data Collection and Extraction procedure (See section **Error! Reference source not found.**).

1. Railways, Roads and Settlements layers were *merged*.
2. A risk *buffer* was applied to the merged layer from step 1. The magnitude of this “Risk Buffer” varied according to the applied scenario (0m, 50m, 100m, or 150m), using 100m as the base case.
3. Protected Areas, Military Areas, High Structures and Air Traffic layers were also *merged* into a single layer.
4. The outputs from steps 1 and 2 were *merged*.
5. Output from step 4 was subjected to an “Operational Radius” *buffer*. The size of the operational area buffer depended on the applied scenario (300m, 650m, 850m, or 1050m), using 425m as the base case.
6. Water Bodies were given a 100m *buffer*.
7. A *buffer* to determine the distance from the GS to forests was applied to the Forests layer. The scenarios explored were 100, 200 and 300m, using 200m as the base case.
8. Outputs from steps 3, 4 and 5 were *merged* into one single layer.
9. The *difference* tool was used using the output from step 6 and the Slope layer.

10. The resulting layer from step 7 was *clipped* to the base map layer from the corresponding region.
11. The tool *multipart to singleparts* was applied to the output layer from the previous step and the output layer was saved.

Using the *batch processing* tool, it was possible to iterate the analysis applying the different sensitivity analysis on the layers (See Figure 4.13). Moreover, all the batch process inputs were saved as .json files to allow validation and quality control.

Figure 4.13. Image showing the batch processing for the site identification analysis.

The final deployment area layers for each region (see Figure 4.14) were saved with a systematic name that would allow the identification of each scenario: "Deployment_Areas_RBxxx_ORxxx_Fxxx_3035_XXX".

RBxxx = 'RB' stands for Risk Buffer and xxx for the number indicating the scenario applied.

ORxxx = 'OR' stands for Operational Radius and xxx for a number indicating the sensitivity analysis applied.

Fxxx = 'F' stands for Forest and xxx for the number indicating the sensitivity analysis applied (distance from forests to the GS).

3035 = indicates the projection.

XXX = Indicates the region code.

Figure 4.14. Ground Station Deployment Areas (in orange) using the base case scenario. Example: Connacht.

Source Data: ©OpenStreetMap Contributors (ODbL), NASA JPL, ©Ireland's Open Data Portal (CC BY 4.0), © Tailte Éireann (CC BY 4.0), © Copernicus (CC BY 4.0), © Irish Lights, © Irish Aviation Authority (IAA)

To obtain the final available sites for AWE deployment and operation at a national level (see example in figure Figure 4.15), one QGIS project was created for each scenario (ten in total), and all the Deployment Areas layers that were generated by region were merged following the next steps:

1. *Merge* all the layers in the project.
2. *Dissolve* the merged layers.
3. Add *auto incremental field* to have a unique identifier for each feature.
4. *Retain* only the field that was created in step 3.
5. Add *geometry attributes* (area and perimeter).
6. *Extract* only the features with Area $\geq 700\text{m}^2$ (See section **Error! Reference source not found.**).
7. Add the Operational Radius *Buffer* specific to each scenario with “dissolve result” activated.
8. Apply the *Multipart to Singlepart* tool.

9. Repeat steps 3 to 5.
10. Export the outputs of step 6 (Deployment Areas) and 9 (Operational Areas), both in shapefile and spreadsheet format.

Both the 'Deployment areas' and 'Operational Areas' layers were named with the same systematic name as explained above.

Figure 4.15. Ground Station Deployment Areas and Operational Areas (in blue) in Ireland using the base case scenario requirements.

Source Data: ©OpenStreetMap Contributors (ODbL), NASA JPL, ©Ireland's Open Data Portal (CC BY 4.0), © Tailte Éireann (CC BY 4.0), © Copernicus (CC BY 4.0), © Irish Lights, © Irish Aviation Authority (IAA)

4.2.2 Capacity calculation

To support the calculation of the technology's capacity in Ireland, the spreadsheet data detailing the area of deployment and operational were utilised. The total available area for AWE GS deployment, the overall operational area, the number of deployment sites, and the capacity of these sites were calculated.

Following the methodology developed for the analysis in Germany, a triangulation method was employed to estimate the maximum number of devices or GS that could be efficiently installed within each designated deployment area.

This triangulation method assumes that the optimum layout for maximising the number of objects (total number >3) within a given area is to place objects in a triangular pattern. In order to apply this method, it is necessary to define the minimum separation distance between objects and the footprint of individual object (i.e., the ground station). In this case the footprint of the ground station was taken as 30m while the minimum separation distance was taken to be 400m.

For N devices > 3 the minimum area required was found to follow a straight line ($R^2 = 0.9992$)

The trendline equation obtained was:

$$y = 157,151x - 472,874$$

where y = minimum area and x = the number of devices.

Note: The triangulation method is a simple technique to estimate the number of devices for a large number of identified sites in an automatic way where the number of sites is too great to define manually or to run layout optimisation techniques. This method works best for sites which are regular in shape and is less accurate for long, elongated or irregular shapes. However, at this scale it seems to give a good first estimate of the number of devices.

In order to estimate the number of devices that could be hosted within the identified areas, specific criteria were applied. Areas ranging from 700m² to 13,800m² were determined suitable for hosting one device⁸, while areas ranging from 13,800m² to 91,540m² could host up to two devices. For areas larger than 91,540m², the trendline equation was utilized to calculate the maximum number of devices that could be supported.

To ensure practicality and realism in the estimation process, all calculated numbers on the number of devices were rounded down to obtain whole numbers. This approach provides a more precise and realistic estimation of the actual number of devices that could be hosted within each respective area.

Once the total number of devices was determined, a direct calculation was conducted to ascertain the potential capacity of the AWE system. This calculation was based on a straightforward conversion rate of either 200 kW or 1.5 MW per device, allowing for a comprehensive assessment of the potential capacity range which is technology specific. The former rate provided a conservative estimate, while the latter yielded a more optimistic estimation, considering power generation capability of different technologies and devices (See results in Section **Error! Reference source not found.**).

4.2.2.1 Correcting factor

As previously introduced in Section 4.1.6 - Settlements, it was necessary to run the model twice to be able to verify the accuracy of the building-related analysis in the study. A key issue in the OSM

⁸ Areas smaller than 700m² (minimum area for a ground station with 30m diameter footprint) were discarded. The shape of certain polygons could have led to overestimation in total deployment area, as the threshold for discarding areas smaller than 700m² may not account for elongated or irregular shapes that meet the minimum required area but that cannot accommodate a 30m diameter device. Developers with smaller diameter requirements may still consider these areas for potential use.

buildings dataset was identified. Approximately 40% of the buildings were listed as NULL in the "type" category, meaning that no information was available regarding the type of building. This lack of classification prevented a comprehensive inclusion of all relevant building types in the analysis. For the purpose of this study, relevant buildings were defined as houses, industrial buildings, other inhabited buildings, or public/commercial buildings, while farming-related structures were ignored in the analysis.

To assess the impact of these NULL values on our results, the analysis was first conducted without using the OSM buildings layer, relying instead on other available layers that provided less complete settlement information. This provided a baseline result for comparison.

In a second run, the analysis was performed using only the buildings that had a valid classification in the "type" category. The unclassified (NULL) buildings were excluded entirely from this run. Of the classified buildings, 49% were identified as relevant (i.e., of the 60% of buildings with valid classification, 49% met the criteria for inclusion). This resulted in a value representing the impact of correctly classified buildings on the final results.

The next step was to calculate a correction factor to adjust for the exclusion of unclassified buildings. The simple ratio method was employed for this purpose. First, the results of the second analysis (with only correctly classified buildings) were compared with the results of the first analysis (without the buildings layer). The ratio was calculated using the formula:

$$Z = 1 - \left(\frac{Y}{X}\right)$$

Where:

Y is the result from the second analysis (with only classified buildings).

X is the result from the first analysis (without any building data).

This ratio (z) was then used to calculate the correction factor, which adjusts for the impact of misclassified (NULL) buildings. The correction was made using the following formula:

$$\text{Corrected Results} = \left(1 - \left(\frac{Z}{29.37 \times 49.26} \right) \right) \times X$$

Where:

29.37 is the total percentage of classified buildings that were of interest (houses, industry, inhabited buildings, etc.).

49.26 is the percentage of classified buildings that were relevant.

Since no additional layers or ground-truth data were available to validate the correction factor, it was assumed that the percentage of misclassified buildings (NULL values) that were relevant would be similar to the percentage of relevant classified buildings.

The corrected results were then presented as a range: one with the corrected values and one with the results from the second run, which excluded all unclassified buildings.

5 Quality Control

Quality control for the data extraction process was implemented by an independent team member who had not been previously involved in the data extraction. This person conducted a visual inspection of all the selected features in each layer of the datasets. At least 20 features in three different states from each dataset were randomly chosen and carefully cross-referenced with corresponding satellite images.

Through this validation procedure, we aimed to ascertain the consistency and accuracy of the extracted data. Any discrepancies or potential errors on the features selection identified during this inspection were promptly rectified through further investigation and refinement of the data selection process.

5.1 Data Extraction and Site Identification

Both the data extraction and the site identification models underwent a validation process that included comparisons with previous analyses conducted manually on two different Irish Counties. To establish the models' accuracy and efficacy, we leveraged a dataset of layers and identified sites that had been previously identified through manual analysis. These layers along with manually identified sites served as a gold standard or benchmark against which the model's performance was measured. The outcomes of the validation process were highly promising, as the model displayed a perfect correlation of 100% with the manually identified sites.

After successfully validating the models, and with the data extraction and site identification stages executed using models developed in the QGIS Graphical Modeller and batch process tools (See Figure 4.13), we were able to monitor and verify the input data for each batch process following the completion of the analysis. This served as a robust quality control mechanism.

Following the generation of output layers from the data extraction and site identification processes, an impartial team member conducted thorough cross-checks to ensure proper generation of each

layer. Additionally, all saved batch processes were reloaded and meticulously examined to verify the accurate completion of input field information. This scrutiny of the outputs and inputs served to uphold the integrity and precision of the entire analysis.

After generating the final layers, an AWE developer cross-referenced certain locations previously identified during a site identification and selection exercise they conducted, noting a remarkably high correlation of suitable sites with this analysis.

6 Results

Following the completion of the site identification process, ten distinct scenarios were generated by considering variations in the risk buffer, operational radius, and distance from the GS to forests. These scenarios allow us to evaluate the impact of these criteria on the availability of areas that are suitable for installing AWE devices.

The results are both presented in Table 6.1 and in the maps presented below. The table showcases the outcomes derived from each scenario applied, allowing the recognition of the significant impact that arises from the use of different requirements.

The key results, i.e., GS Deployment Area, Number of Devices, Minimum Capacity and Maximum Capacity, from Table 6.1 have been visualised in Figure 6.1, Figure 6.2, Figure 6.3, and Figure 6.4 respectively.

Table 6.1. Results of the site identification analysis applying different scenarios. Base Case highlighted in orange.

Test Case	Outer Operational Area (km ²)	GS Deployment Area (km ²)	N° of Sites	N° of devices	Min Capacity* (MW)	Max Capacity** (MW)
Base Case†	9,296 - 10,663	1,598 - 1,807	5,984	21,444 - 24,454	4,289 - 4,891	32,166 - 36,681
0m Risk Buffer	1,6347 -18,073	2,465 - 2,790	12,241 - 13,157	36,203 - 40,180	7,241 - 8,036	54,304 - 60,270
50m Risk Buffer	12,306 - 13,891	1,963 - 2,227	9,156 - 10,119	27,760 - 31,315	5,552 - 6,263	41,639 - 46,973
150m Risk Buffer	7,119 - 8,234	1,330 - 1,493	5,089 - 5,851	16,837 - 19,263	3,367 - 3,853	25,256 - 28,895
300m Op. Radius	13,910- 15,305	2,952 - 3,330	15,118 - 16,047	14,173 - 18,633	8,835 - 9,727	66,259 - 72,950
650m Op. Radius	4,400 - 5,125	719 - 776	1,736 - 2,083	7,414 - 8,362	1,483 - 1,672	11,121 - 12,543
850m Op. Radius	2,734 - 3,052	411 - 434	822 - 939	3,936 - 4,263	787 - 853	5,904 - 6,395
1050m Op. Radius	1,987- 2,107	244 - 257	527 - 564	2,376 - 2,509	475 - 502	3,563 - 3,764
100m Distance to forests	11,800 - 13,408	2,010 - 2,287	9,106 - 10,182	27,757 - 31,546	5,551 - 6,309	41,636 - 47,319
300m Distance to forests	7,261 - 8,345	1,289 - 1,448	5,204 - 5,923	16,810 - 19,145	3,362 - 3,829	25,215 - 28,718

† Base case: Operational Radius 425m, 100m risk buffer and 200m distance to forests.

* Minimum capacity contemplates a capacity of 200 kW per device.

** Maximum capacity contemplates a capacity of 1.5 MW per device.

All scenarios exhibit a high number of potential sites in Ireland, ranging from 527 (1,050 m OR) to 16,047 (300m OR) potentially suitable locations. The base case analysis (RB100, OR425, F200) identified between 9,300 and 10,700 km² of outer operational space, and between 1,600 and 1,800 km² of deployment area in the Republic of Ireland suitable for potential AWE deployment. This base case area has the potential to support an estimated AWE capacity of up to 32 to 36 GW (assuming an individual device capacity of 1.5 MW). Among the scenarios evaluated, the most advantageous involved reducing the operational radius to 300m. As a result, this adjustment yielded an operational space of roughly 14,000 to 15,000 km² suitable for AWE deployment, allowing for a greater number of devices with a potential capacity of between 8 to 73 GW, contingent upon the capacity of each individual device.

Across the base case, the 0m risk buffer, the 50m risk buffer, the 150m risk buffer, and scenarios altering the distance to forests, a similar capacity per unit area is evident (ranging from 0.45 to 0.47 MW/km² for 200 KW/device and 3.32 to 3.53 MW/km² for 1.5MW/device). Notably, the primary influencing factor on this metric is the tether length, i.e., operational radius. As can be seen in Figure 6.1, Figure 6.2, Figure 6.3, and Figure 6.4, the graphs of the risk buffer and distance to forests scenarios are broadly linear, with an inverse relationship between each parameter and distance, while the slope of the operational radius is curved, showing a steeper decrease in each parameter as the operational radius cases increase. The scenario featuring a 300m operational radius demonstrates a notably higher capacity per unit area (0.63 MW/km² for 200 KW/device and 4.77 MW/km² for 1.5MW/device) compared to others, while the 1050m tether displays the lowest capacity per unit area of all scenarios analysed (0.23 MW/km² for 200 KW/device and 1.79 MW/km² for 1.5MW/device). These capacity per unit area results align with the power density capacity calculated in other studies on AWE Power Potential conducted by TU Delft within the JustWind4All project. These studies assumed a power density of 2 MW/km² for onshore AWE soft wing technology.

Figure 6.1. Total area (km²) suitable for GS deployment in the scenarios studied. The results are grouped by modified parameters to assist with the visualization. To facilitate comparison, the base case (the blue bar) is present in the three groups. The wider, translucent bars represent the maximum value, while the narrower, solid-coloured bars represent the minimum value.

Figure 6.2. Total number of devices that can be deployed in each of the scenarios studied. The results are grouped by modified parameters to assist with the visualization. To facilitate comparison, the base case (the blue bar) is present in the three groups. The wider, translucent bars represent the maximum value, while the narrower, solid-coloured bars represent the minimum value.

Figure 6.3. Capacity in MW that can be deployed in each of the scenarios studied (based on devices with a 200kW capacity). The results are grouped by modified parameters to assist with the visualization. To facilitate comparison, the base case (the blue bar) is present in the three groups. The wider, translucent bars represent the maximum value, while the narrower, solid-coloured bars represent the minimum value.

Figure 6.4. Capacity in MW that can be deployed in each of the scenarios studied (based on devices with a 1.5MW capacity). The results are grouped by modified parameters to assist with the visualization. To facilitate comparison, the base case (the blue bar) is present in the three groups. The wider, translucent bars represent the maximum value, while the narrower, solid-coloured bars represent the minimum value.

The maps showcasing the identified areas corresponding to each scenario are presented below:

Figure 6.5. Map showing suitable sites in Ireland after applying the base case scenario requirements. Zoom in to show the granularity of the identifies sites. The red point marks the location of the existing test Site in County Mayo.

Figure 6.6. Map showing suitable sites in Ireland after applying the 0m Risk Buffer scenario requirements.

Figure 6.7. Map showing suitable sites in Ireland after applying the 50m Risk Buffer scenario requirements.

Figure 6.8. Map showing suitable sites in Ireland after applying the 150m Risk Buffer scenario requirements.

Figure 6.9. Map showing suitable sites in Ireland after applying the 300m Operational Radius scenario requirements.

Figure 6.10. Map showing suitable sites in Ireland after applying the 650m Operational Radius scenario requirements.

Figure 6.11. Map showing suitable sites in Ireland after applying the 850m Operational Radius scenario requirements.

Figure 6.12. Map showing suitable sites in Ireland after applying the 1050m Operational Radius scenario requirements.

Figure 6.13. Map showing suitable sites in Ireland after applying the 100m from GS to forests scenario requirements.

Figure 6.14. Map showing Suitable sites in Ireland after applying the 300m from GS to forests scenario requirements.

7 Summary

7.1 Main Insights

Based on the maps shown in Section 6, there are many areas within The Republic of Ireland potentially suitable for the deployment of AWE devices. There are areas with very few suitable sites that largely correspond to mountainous areas (e.g., Burren, McGillicuddy's Reeks and the Wicklow Mountains) or urban areas, particularly cities and large towns. The areas with large, contiguous areas are County Mayo, County Donegal, and County Kerry particularly on its southwestern border with County Cork. These areas persist within each map, even under the 1050m OR scenario, which suggests they may have a high capacity for larger or denser AWE deployments. The Bangor Eris AWE test site in County Mayo can be found in one such area.

Results: Relative to other countries, e.g. Germany (Coca-Tagarro, 2023), Ireland is a very promising location for the deployment of AWE. In the Base Case (Operational Radius 425m, 100m risk buffer and 200m distance to forests) 5,984 sites were identified, allowing up to 24,454 devices to be installed. With 200 kW per AWE system, this translates to 4,289 - 4,891 MW of potential capacity; using 1.5 MW AWE systems, the capacity would rise to 32,166 - 36,681 MW.

The graphs and maps in Section 6 show the results of running the model with the different risk buffer, operational radius and distance to forests parameters. A higher proportion of the Republic of Ireland's landmass is available as a potential AWE when compared to the previous study on Germany (Coca-Tagarro, 2023). This may be a result of the lower population density and more dispersed population in Ireland compared to Germany, at 72.42 people per square kilometre⁹ to Germany's

⁹ <https://www.macrotrends.net/global-metrics/countries/IRL/ireland/population-density>

233 people per square kilometre¹⁰. It may also be related to physical geography such as Germany's high forest coverage, 32.68%¹¹ compared to Ireland's 11.6%¹².

Impact of operational radius: Among the parameters examined, the sensitivity analysis identified the operational radius as having the most substantial effect on the results. The operational radius is directly correlated to the tether length used by AWE developers. Adjusting the operational radius can lead to notable variations in the outcomes of the analysis, highlighting the need for careful consideration and optimisation of this parameter to ensure accurate and effective decision-making regarding GS deployment. As can be seen in Section 6, there is a much more significant reduction in the results of the model as the operational radius increases, especially when compared to the more linear reduction in the other parameters. It is important for developers to find the right balance between their technology's ideal operational requirements for exploiting high-altitude wind and the availability of suitable sites. They will need to carefully study and assess the trade-offs associated with different operational radius to optimise the deployment potential while considering factors such as wind resource availability, airspace constraints, and technological limitations. Striking the right balance ensures that AWE technology can effectively harness high-altitude wind resources while maximising the number of viable deployment sites.

Correction Factor: Due to time and data constraints, the correction factor was calculated based on the assumption that the percentage of relevant buildings in the unclassified (NULL) dataset is similar to that in the classified dataset. While this approach was the best feasible option, it introduces some potential caveats. The impact of unclassified buildings may differ from that of classified ones, and relying on this assumption could lead to over or underestimation. For instance, the model does not

¹⁰ <https://eurydice.eacea.ec.europa.eu/national-education-systems/germany/population-demographic-situation-languages-and-religions>

¹¹ <https://www.statista.com/statistics/435658/forest-area-as-percentage-of-land-area-germany/>

¹² <https://www.teagasc.ie/news--events/daily/forestry/irelands-forests---statistics-2023.php>

account for potential variations in the data such as unclassified buildings having a different proportion of relevant and irrelevant types, unclassified buildings could be more concentrated in certain areas, or vary in size and scale, and there was no sensitivity analysis performed due to lack of alternative data sources. However, despite these limitations, this approach was the most practical given the available resources.

7.2 Recommendations

- The findings of this report emphasize the significance of accurate and comprehensive data in identifying suitable sites for Airborne Wind Energy (AWE) deployment. The current analysis highlights gaps in certain datasets, such as incomplete classification of buildings and inconsistencies in forest cover data. These limitations can introduce biases and reduce the reliability of site identification. To address this, investment in refining existing datasets and integrating new datasets is recommended. Emerging datasets from satellite imaging and updated government repositories could provide higher resolution and more current geographic, environmental, and infrastructure data. For example, leveraging AI-enhanced satellite data for forest canopy density or urban sprawl can address current gaps. Comparing multiple datasets for the same parameter, as demonstrated in this report, should remain a standard practice to ensure data integrity and accuracy.
- While the GIS model identifies potential AWE deployment sites with precision, the findings must be considered as a preliminary framework requiring validation on the ground. Like all GIS analysis, this study is constrained by data resolution and static assumptions which may not accurately reflect the real situation on site. Ground truthing ensures the practicality of the selected sites by validating site conditions and alignment with developers technology specific operational requirements.
- It is highly recommended to continue expanding these studies to other European countries due to their significant value in providing valuable insights and informing decision-making processes. As of the writing of this report, Germany had previously been studied (Coca-

Tagarro, 2023), and studies on the Netherlands, France and Spain are underway. By conducting these studies in additional countries, a broader perspective can be gained, allowing for a better understanding of the factors influencing site selection across different regions. Moreover, this expansion would enable organizations to identify trends, similarities, and differences in site suitability, considering diverse geographical, economic, and regulatory contexts. Ultimately, such comprehensive studies across multiple countries can help optimize resource allocation, minimize risks, and maximize the potential for successful deployments. Additionally, understanding the capacity of AWEs at a European level will facilitate assessing feasibility and economic viability. It will help comparing energy generation capabilities with existing sources and guide decision-making. Governments, regulators, and stakeholders can set goals and policies based on this information. Identifying high-capacity areas can enable focused efforts for maximum energy generation potential. It will also be helpful in providing suitable areas for the deployment of AWE where devices can be tested in real world conditions which will provide more data and learnings that will further enable their rollout into other countries with different prevailing conditions.

- Future studies should adopt a more flexible approach that considers varying developer requirements. Each developer or organisation may have unique preferences, priorities, or constraints that influence site selection. Therefore, it is recommended to develop a framework that allows for customisation and adaptation to individual developer needs. Moreover, incorporating a comprehensive wind profile analysis is crucial to improve the accuracy and applicability of the results. By considering detailed wind profiles, including factors such as wind direction, speed, and turbulence, the analysis can provide more precise estimations of energy generation potential. This information is vital for optimising the layout and positioning of the technology, leading to more effective and efficient deployments.